

BLOCKCHAIN-ENABLED SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT: IMPLICATIONS FOR THE LAND TRANSPORTATION SECTOR**Todor Koritarov***Assistant professor, PhD,**Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy, Varna, Republic of Bulgaria*<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7712-8235>**Abstract**

Blockchain technology is effecting a transformation in land transportation, enhancing both the efficiency and security of supply chains. This paper delineates the principal attributes of blockchain technology, including decentralization, transparency, and security, and their ramifications for transportation systems. The integration of blockchain technology can enhance traceability, optimize operational efficiency, and cultivate trust among stakeholders while guaranteeing data integrity. It presents opportunities for regulatory compliance, cost reduction, and sustainability, particularly when integrated with IoT devices for enhanced monitoring. Nevertheless, obstacles such as technical complexities and regulatory ambiguities may impede the comprehensive adoption of this technology. Future research should concentrate on the practical implementation and scalability of blockchain technology, with the transportation sector assuming an active role in the development of applications that will facilitate more efficient and sustainable supply chains.

Keywords: blockchain, supply chain management, land transportation, decentralization, transparency, security, smart contracts

1. Introduction

Blockchain technology has evolved into a transformative force in the domain of land transportation, offering substantial potential for enhancing the efficiency and security of supply chains. The implementation of blockchain technology within land transportation frameworks has the potential to revolutionize supply chain management. It can offer enhanced traceability, increased efficiency through the use of smart contracts, and improved data security.

Blockchain technology has been the subject of investigation across sectors – finance technology, healthcare, and supply chain management. However, its applications in the field of land transportation remain in a relatively nascent state. Despite the growing interest in blockchain technology for land transportation, there is a deficiency of comprehensive research examining its conceptual characteristics and implications for the sector.

This paper aims to fill the knowledge deficiency by exploring the conceptual characteristics of blockchain technology and examining their implications for the land transportation sector.

The research question of the paper is: In what ways can blockchain technology improve efficiency and security within the land transportation supply chain?

The objective of this paper is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the potential applications of blockchain technology in land transportation and its implications for supply chain management.

The paper posits that the integration of blockchain technology in land transportation systems has the potential to revolutionize supply chain management. This would be achieved by enabling enhanced traceability, improved efficiency through smart contracts, and heightened data security.

2. Conceptual characteristics of blockchain technology: decentralization, transparency, and security

Blockchain technology represents a revolutionary advancement in digital data management, exhibiting a distinctive set of conceptual elements that differentiate it from traditional systems. In essence, blockchain functions as a decentralized and distributed ledger technology, ensuring data integrity through its immutable and transparent nature. This implies that once information is entered into the blockchain, it cannot be modified or erased, which greatly enhances the reliability of the data and the trust among users and stakeholders[1]. The blockchain's decentralized structure eliminates the necessity for a central authority, facilitating direct interactions between peers that enhance autonomy and provide greater control over data[2].

A principal attribute of blockchain technology is its transparency. Each transaction is recorded on a public ledger that can be accessed by all network participants. This not only encourages accountability but also enhances the ability to trace transactions[3]. The aforementioned clarity is of vital importance in a multitude of applications, including those pertaining to supply chain management. It can assist in the reduction of issues associated with information asymmetry and enhance operational efficiency[4]. Furthermore, the implementation of consensus mechanisms ensures that all participants concur on the veracity of transactions, thereby enhancing the reliability of the recorded data[2][5].

The security of data is a fundamental aspect of blockchain technology. The deployment of cryptographic techniques ensures the secure storage and transmission of data, preventing unauthorized access and modification[6]. This is particularly pertinent in sectors such as healthcare and finance, where the safeguarding of data privacy is of paramount importance[7]. Furthermore, the utilisation of smart contracts—self-executing agreements wherein the stipulations are integrated directly into the code—offers an additional layer of security and automation, enabling transactions that are more expedient and reliable[8].

In addition to these foundational characteristics, blockchain technology offers the crucial benefits of scalability and adaptability, which are essential for its integration across diverse sectors. As organizations increasingly seek to leverage blockchain for a spectrum of applications, including supply chain management and the Internet of Things (IoT), the capacity to expand solutions while maintaining performance and security is of paramount importance[9]. The ongoing evolution of blockchain technology, including the development of hybrid models that combine public and private blockchains, enhances its capacity to address complex challenges in a more effective and efficient manner[10][11].

The defining characteristics of blockchain technology—decentralization, transparency, security, and scalability—establish it as a transformative tool with the potential to revolutionize a multitude of industries. This is due to its capacity to enhance trust, optimize operational efficiency, and maintain data integrity. As research continues to examine the potential applications of blockchain technology, it is anticipated that its impact will continue to grow, fostering innovation and influencing the way conventional business practices are conducted[12][13][14].

Following an examination of the fundamental characteristics of blockchain technology, it is essential to investigate its practical applications within the land transportation industry. The implementation of blockchain technology in this sector presents a unique opportunity to address persistent challenges in supply chain management, particularly those related to efficiency and security. The land transportation sector has the potential to undergo a transformative shift through the harnessing of the decentralized, transparent, and secure qualities inherent to blockchain technology. This could result in the implementation of more efficient processes, a reduction in fraud, and enhanced traceability. The following section will examine the practical applications of blockchain technology in land transportation systems, with a particular focus on its impact on supply chain efficiency and security protocols.

3. Blockchain integration in land transportation: enhancing supply chain efficiency and security

The implementation of blockchain technology in land transportation, particularly in the context of supply chain management, presents a substantial opportunity to enhance efficiency, transparency, and security. The following paragraphs delineate the various methods through which blockchain technology can be integrated into land transportation systems, with a particular focus on its applications in supply chain management.

Enhanced traceability and transparency

Blockchain technology offers a decentralized and immutable record that enhances traceability and transparency throughout the supply chain. This feature is of particular importance in the context of land transportation, where goods can be tracked in real time. By recording each transaction and movement on a blockchain, all stakeholders can access a single, authoritative source of information regarding the status and location of shipments. This reduces the likelihood of discrepancies and fosters trust among participants in the supply chain[15][16][17]. For example, the capacity to trace

the origin of products can significantly reduce the probability of fraud and theft, as all transactions are meticulously documented and subject to continuous review[18][19].

Improved efficiency through smart contracts

Self-executing agreements, otherwise known as smart contracts, have their terms embedded in code, thereby enabling the automation of a multitude of processes within the domain of land transportation. The implementation of smart contracts on a blockchain enables transportation firms to enhance their operational efficiency, including the automation of payment processing, shipment tracking, and compliance management[20]. Upon arrival of a shipment at its destination, the smart contract can automatically initiate payment to the carrier, thereby reducing delays and administrative burdens[21][22]. The implementation of automation facilitates the expeditious completion of transactions while concomitantly diminishing the probability of human error, thereby engendering more reliable operational outcomes[23].

Enhanced security and data integrity

The cryptographic features of blockchain technology ensure the security and integrity of the data stored within the system, preventing any form of tampering or alteration. This is particularly crucial in the context of land transportation, where the confidentiality and integrity of data pertaining to shipments, including details such as ownership and condition, must be protected against unauthorized access and modifications[24][25]. Blockchain technology provides transportation firms with a means of safeguarding their data from cyber threats and ensuring that all stakeholders have access to accurate and up-to-date information[26]. The enhanced security measures may enhance confidence among stakeholders, thereby fostering more robust collaborative relationships throughout the supply chain[27][28].

Streamlined regulatory compliance

Compliance with regulations represents a pivotal concern within the transportation sector, particularly with regard to safety protocols and environmental legislation. Blockchain technology can facilitate compliance by providing a transparent and immutable record of all transactions and procedures pertaining to the transportation of goods. [29]. This feature allows businesses to demonstrate their compliance with regulations with minimal effort, as all necessary documentation can be stored on the blockchain and made available to regulatory authorities in real-time[30][31]. Furthermore, the ability to rapidly retrieve historical data can streamline the auditing and inspection processes, reducing the time and resources required for compliance management[32].

Improved collaboration and coordination

Blockchain technology facilitates collaboration among diverse participants in the supply chain, including manufacturers, carriers, and retailers. Blockchain provides a unified platform for data sharing, enabling all stakeholders to access consistent information, thereby enhancing coordination and decision-making[33][34]. To illustrate, the ability to monitor the status of shipments in real time can facilitate more efficient inventory management and enhance logistics processes for businesses[35]. This collaborative approach

to problem-solving can lead to reduced lead times, lower costs, and greater customer satisfaction. It allows stakeholders to respond more effectively to changes in demand or disruptions in the supply chain[36].

Cost reduction

The implementation of blockchain technology has the potential to significantly reduce the costs associated with land transportation. By reducing the necessity for intermediaries and manual processes, businesses can diminish the expenses associated with logistics management[37]. Furthermore, the enhanced efficiency and precision offered by blockchain can mitigate delays and losses, which contributes to a reduction in costs[38]. The potential for reduced insurance premiums as a consequence of enhanced security and diminished fraud risk also represents a financial advantage for businesses that adopt blockchain solutions[39][40].

Sustainability and environmental impact

Blockchain technology has the potential to significantly enhance sustainability in the supply chain by providing improved tracking of carbon emissions and adherence to environmental regulations. By recording the environmental impact of transportation activities on the blockchain, businesses can gain insights into their sustainability performance and identify areas for improvement[41]. Such transparency can also enhance corporate social responsibility initiatives, as stakeholders are increasingly demanding accountability for environmental practices[42][43][44]. Furthermore, blockchain technology can facilitate the observation of sustainable practices throughout the supply chain, ensuring that all parties adhere to the established standards[45][46].

Integration with IoT for enhanced monitoring

The integration of blockchain technology and Internet of Things (IoT) devices has the potential to markedly enhance the efficacy of monitoring functions in land transportation. Internet of Things (IoT) sensors have the capacity to gather real-time data on a range of factors, including temperature, humidity, and location. This data can then be securely stored on the blockchain[20][43]. This approach allows for the proactive monitoring of shipments, particularly those containing items that require special handling, such as pharmaceuticals and perishable goods[32][47]. The integration of IoT data into a blockchain enables businesses to ensure that products are delivered under optimal conditions, thereby reducing waste and enhancing quality[48].

Facilitating Cross-Border Trade

Blockchain technology has the potential to facilitate cross-border trade in a more efficient and expedient manner by providing a secure and transparent platform for the recording of transactions and adherence to international regulatory standards[21]. The implementation of blockchain technology can facilitate the simplification of customs clearance and regulatory approvals processes by streamlining documentation and automating procedures through the use of smart contracts[23]. This functionality not only facilitates the expeditious transfer of products between countries but also enhances confidence among global trading partners, as all parties can confirm the legitimacy and adherence of the shipments[22][49].

Future trends and innovations

As blockchain technology continues to evolve, it is anticipated that its applications in land transportation and supply chain management will expand. The advent of permissioned blockchains and the integration of artificial intelligence with blockchain systems may potentially enhance the efficacy of supply chain management[34][50]. Furthermore, ongoing research on the scaling and interoperability of blockchain technology is anticipated to address existing limitations, thereby enhancing its applicability for a broader range of uses within the transportation sector[16][51]. Blockchain's capacity to facilitate innovative solutions, including the implementation of decentralized logistics systems and enhanced data sharing, establishes it as a pivotal element in the prospective advancement of land transportation[17][31].

In light of this investigation into the prospective influence of blockchain technology on land transportation systems and supply chain management, it is imperative to integrate our findings and contemplate their far-reaching implications. The following section will provide a synthesis of the key insights from this study, evaluate the significance of blockchain integration in the land transportation sector, and propose future directions for research and implementation.

4. Conclusion

The incorporation of blockchain technology into land transportation systems and supply chain management offers considerable promise for a radical transformation of the industry. This study has identified several key benefits, including enhanced transparency, improved traceability, increased security, and streamlined processes. By capitalizing on the decentralized and immutable nature of blockchain technology, stakeholders can enhance trust, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness throughout the supply chain.

The research findings illustrate that blockchain implementation can effectively address longstanding challenges in land transportation, including fraud prevention, real-time tracking, and seamless information sharing among multiple parties. These improvements have the potential to optimize logistics operations, reduce delays, and minimize errors, thereby increasing customer satisfaction[52] and conferring a competitive advantage on businesses that adopt this technology.

Nevertheless, it is crucial to recognize that the extensive implementation of blockchain technology in land transportation systems is confronted with a multitude of challenges. These include technical challenges, regulatory uncertainties, and the necessity for standardization across the industry[53]. To surmount these obstacles, it will be necessary for a number of stakeholders, including technology providers, transportation companies, government agencies, and academic institutions[54][55], to engage in collaborative endeavours.

Future research should concentrate on the development of practical implementation strategies, the resolution of scalability issues, and the investigation of the integration of blockchain with other emerging technologies[56][54], including the Internet of Things (IoT) and artificial intelligence. Moreover, the implementation of pilot projects and case studies across diverse transportation modes and supply chain scenarios will facilitate the acquisition of invaluable insights into the

practical applicability and advantages of blockchain technology in real-world contexts.

In conclusion, while blockchain technology demonstrates considerable potential for transforming land transportation systems and supply chain management, its full potential remains unrealized. As the technology continues to evolve and mature, it is of the utmost importance for industry leaders and policymakers to remain informed about its developments and to actively participate in shaping its future applications. By embracing the capabilities of blockchain technology and addressing the challenges associated with its implementation, the land transportation sector can facilitate the development of a more efficient, secure, and sustainable future in supply chain management.

References

1. S. DAVIDSON, P. DE FILIPPI, and J. POTTS, "Blockchains and the economic institutions of capitalism," *Journal of Institutional Economics*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 639–658, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1017/S1744137417000200.
2. Z. Zhao, Y. Liu, H. Zhao, and Y. Wang, "A Video Security Verification Method Based on Blockchain," in *2023 IEEE International Conference on Blockchain (Blockchain)*, IEEE, Dec. 2023, pp. 105–108. doi: 10.1109/Blockchain60715.2023.00026.
3. H. Song, S. Han, and K. Yu, "Blockchain-enabled supply chain operations and financing: the perspective of expectancy theory," *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, vol. 43, no. 12, pp. 1943–1975, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1108/IJOPM-07-2022-0467.
4. Sheel and V. Nath, "Effect of blockchain technology adoption on supply chain adaptability, agility, alignment and performance," *Management Research Review*, vol. 42, no. 12, pp. 1353–1374, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1108/MRR-12-2018-0490.
5. X. Lu, S. Fu, C. Jiang, and P. Lio, "A Fine-Grained IoT Data Access Control Scheme Combining Attribute-Based Encryption and Blockchain," *Security and Communication Networks*, vol. 2021, pp. 1–13, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1155/2021/5308206.
6. J. Guruprakash and S. Koppu, "EC-ElGamal and Genetic Algorithm-Based Enhancement for Lightweight Scalable Blockchain in IoT Domain," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 141269–141281, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3013282.
7. D. Zhang, S. Wang, Y. Zhang, Q. Zhang, and Y. Zhang, "A Secure and Privacy-Preserving Medical Data Sharing via Consortium Blockchain," *Security and Communication Networks*, vol. 2022, pp. 1–15, May 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/2759787.
8. Z. SUN, D. Han, D. Li, X. Wang, C.-C. Chang, and Z. Wu, "A Blockchain-based Secure Storage Scheme for Medical Information," Jan. 25, 2022. doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-1201585/v1.
9. K.-P. Huang, S. Lo, and D. Sutthiphisal, "From Data Transparency and Security to Interfirm Collaboration-A Blockchain Technology Perspective," *ABAC Journal*, vol. 43, no. 3, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.59865/abacj.2023.27.
10. P. Jahanbin, R. S. Sharma, S. T. Wingreen, N. Kshetri, and K. R. Choo, "Towards CRISP-BC: 3TIC specification framework for Blockchain use-cases," *IET Blockchain*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 159–168, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1049/blc2.12038.
11. E. F. M. Komdeur and P. T. M. Ingenbleek, "The potential of blockchain technology in the procurement of sustainable timber products," *International Wood Products Journal*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 249–257, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1080/20426445.2021.1967624.
12. D. Meijer and J. Ubacht, "The governance of blockchain systems from an institutional perspective, a matter of trust or control?," in *Proceedings of the 19th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research: Governance in the Data Age*, New York, NY, USA: ACM, May 2018, pp. 1–9. doi: 10.1145/3209281.3209321.
13. Alammery, S. Alhazmi, M. Almasri, and S. Gillani, "Blockchain-Based Applications in Education: A Systematic Review," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 12, p. 2400, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.3390/app9122400.
14. M. Klöckner, C. G. Schmidt, and S. M. Wagner, "When Blockchain Creates Shareholder Value: Empirical Evidence from International Firm Announcements," *Prod Oper Manag*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 46–64, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1111/poms.13609.
15. H. Treiblmaier, "The impact of the blockchain on the supply chain: a theory-based research framework and a call for action," *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 545–559, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1108/SCM-01-2018-0029.
16. P. Helo and Y. Hao, "Blockchains in operations and supply chains: A model and reference implementation," *Comput Ind Eng*, vol. 136, pp. 242–251, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.cie.2019.07.023.
17. M. K. Lim, Y. Li, C. Wang, and M.-L. Tseng, "A literature review of blockchain technology applications in supply chains: A comprehensive analysis of themes, methodologies and industries," *Comput Ind Eng*, vol. 154, p. 107133, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.cie.2021.107133.
18. Erol et al., "Assessing the feasibility of blockchain technology in industries: evidence from Turkey," *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 746–769, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1108/JEIM-09-2019-0309.
19. G. Jain, H. Singh, K. R. Chaturvedi, and S. Rakesh, "Blockchain in logistics industry: in fizza customer trust or not," *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 541–558, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1108/JEIM-06-2018-0142.
20. M. A. Alqarni, M. S. Alkathiri, S. H. Chaudhary, and S. Saleem, "Use of Blockchain-Based Smart Contracts in Logistics and Supply Chains," *Electronics (Basel)*, vol. 12, no. 6, p. 1340, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.3390/electronics12061340.
21. E. Tijan, S. Aksentijević, K. Ivanić, and M. Jardas, "Blockchain Technology Implementation in Logistics," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 4, p. 1185, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.3390/su11041185.
22. H. Magd, M. S. A. Ansari, and S. Negi, "Impact of Blockchain Technology on Operations and Supply Chain Management Performance," in *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Innovation in Information Technology and Business (ICIITB 2022)*,

- Dordrecht: Atlantis Press International BV, 2023, pp. 22–35. doi: 10.2991/978-94-6463-110-4_3.
23. Tan, W. P. Wong, C. K. Tan, S. Jomthanachai, and C. P. Lim, “Blockchain-based Logistics 4.0: enhancing performance of logistics service providers,” *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 1442–1463, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.1108/APJML-07-2023-0650.
24. Al-Jaroodi and N. Mohamed, “Blockchain in Industries: A Survey,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 36500–36515, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2903554.
25. B. L. AYLAK, “The Effects of the Applications of Blockchain Technology on the Logistics sector,” *European Journal of Science and Technology*, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.31590/ejosat.1077800.
26. Z. Acar and O. E. Clarke, “Applicability Of Blockchain Technology In The Global Logistics Systems,” Dec. 2021, pp. 236–246. doi: 10.15405/epsbs.2021.12.04.24.
27. Dobrovnik, D. M. Herold, E. Fürst, and S. Kummer, “Blockchain for and in Logistics: What to Adopt and Where to Start,” *Logistics*, vol. 2, no. 3, p. 18, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.3390/logistics2030018.
28. S. Saberi, M. Kouhizadeh, J. Sarkis, and L. Shen, “Blockchain technology and its relationships to sustainable supply chain management,” *Int J Prod Res*, vol. 57, no. 7, pp. 2117–2135, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1080/00207543.2018.1533261.
29. W. Wen, “Research on the Cooperation Strategy of Rail-road Transportation Enterprises under the Participation of Blockchain Technology,” *Industrial Engineering and Innovation Management*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2023, doi: 10.23977/ieim.2023.061002.
30. K. Paardenkooper, “Creating value for Small and Medium Enterprises with the logistic applications of blockchain,” in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Digital Technologies in Logistics and Infrastructure (ICDTLI 2019)*, Paris, France: Atlantis Press, 2019. doi: 10.2991/icdtli-19.2019.48.
31. R. M. Difrancesco, P. Meena, and G. Kumar, “How blockchain technology improves sustainable supply chain processes: a practical guide,” *Operations Management Research*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 620–641, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s12063-022-00343-y.
32. Alrowaily, M. Alghamdi, I. Alkhazi, A. B. Hassanat, M. M. S. Arbab, and C. Z. Liu, “Modeling and Analysis of Proof-Based Strategies for Distributed Consensus in Blockchain-Based Peer-to-Peer Networks,” *Sustainability*, vol. 15, no. 2, p. 1478, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.3390/su15021478.
33. Raja Santhi and P. Muthuswamy, “Influence of Blockchain Technology in Manufacturing Supply Chain and Logistics,” *Logistics*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 15, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.3390/logistics6010015.
34. T. Khanna, P. Nand, and V. Bali, “Permissioned Blockchain Model for End-to-End Trackability in Supply Chain Management,” *International Journal of e-Collaboration*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 45–58, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.4018/IJeC.2020010104.
35. P. J. Zelbst, K. W. Green, V. E. Sower, and P. L. Bond, “The impact of RFID, IIoT, and Blockchain technologies on supply chain transparency,” *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 441–457, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1108/JMTM-03-2019-0118.
36. Litke, D. Anagnostopoulos, and T. Varvarigou, “Blockchains for Supply Chain Management: Architectural Elements and Challenges Towards a Global Scale Deployment,” *Logistics*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 5, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.3390/logistics3010005.
37. Meyliana et al., “The Implementation of Business Process Blockchain Technology Based of MSCWR SmartBox Model,” *Indonesian Journal of Information Systems*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 68–80, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.24002/ijis.v5i2.6793.
38. R. Azzi, R. K. Chamoun, and M. Sokhn, “The power of a blockchain-based supply chain,” *Comput Ind Eng*, vol. 135, pp. 582–592, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.cie.2019.06.042.
39. K. O. Park, “A Study on Sustainable Usage Intention of Blockchain in the Big Data Era: Logistics and Supply Chain Management Companies,” *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 24, p. 10670, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.3390/su122410670.
40. Kouhizadeh and J. Sarkis, “Blockchain Practices, Potentials, and Perspectives in Greening Supply Chains,” *Sustainability*, vol. 10, no. 10, p. 3652, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.3390/su10103652.
41. M. Uddin et al., “From Hype to Reality: Unveiling the Promises, Challenges and Opportunities of Blockchain in Supply Chain Systems,” *Sustainability*, vol. 15, no. 16, p. 12193, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.3390/su151612193.
42. S. Velinov, “DECARBONIZATION OF MARITIME INDUSTRY,” *Списание Морско право и индустрия*, vol. 2, pp. 183–191, 2024, Accessed: Oct. 20, 2024. [Online]. Available: [https://maritime.vfu.bg/files/Svilen%20Velinov,%20Decarbonization%20of%20Maritime%20Industry%20\(%D0%92%D0%92%D0%9C%D0%A3\).pdf](https://maritime.vfu.bg/files/Svilen%20Velinov,%20Decarbonization%20of%20Maritime%20Industry%20(%D0%92%D0%92%D0%9C%D0%A3).pdf)
43. Rejeb, J. G. Keogh, and H. Treiblmaier, “Leveraging the Internet of Things and Blockchain Technology in Supply Chain Management,” *Future Internet*, vol. 11, no. 7, p. 161, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.3390/fi11070161.
44. K. P. K. M. Gouri Shankar Mishra, Sachin Kumar, Abhishek Sharma, “Ensuring Logistics Integrity: An Ethereum Framework,” *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, vol. 11, no. 11, pp. 819–830, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.17762/ijritcc.v11i11.10229.
45. Y. Wang, M. Singgih, J. Wang, and M. Rit, “Making sense of blockchain technology: How will it transform supply chains?,” *Int J Prod Econ*, vol. 211, pp. 221–236, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2019.02.002.
46. C.-H. Wu, Y.-P. Tsang, C. K.-M. Lee, and W.-K. Ching, “A Blockchain-IoT Platform for the Smart Pallet Pooling Management,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 18, p. 6310, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21186310.
47. J. Chen, S. Xu, K. Liu, S. Yao, X. Luo, and H. Wu, “Intelligent Transportation Logistics Optimal Warehouse Location Method Based on Internet of Things and Blockchain Technology,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 4, p. 1544, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22041544.

48. L. Zhang, L. Hang, and D. Kim, "Enhanced Multiset Consensus Protocol Based on PBFT for Logistics Information Traceability," *Security and Communication Networks*, vol. 2023, pp. 1–16, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1155/2023/1525998.
49. M. Teodorescu and E. Korchagina, "Applying Blockchain in the Modern Supply Chain Management: Its Implication on Open Innovation," *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 80, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.3390/joitmc7010080.
50. M. Petersen, N. Hackius, and B. von See, "Mapping the sea of opportunities: Blockchain in supply chain and logistics," *Information Technology*, vol. 60, no. 5–6, pp. 263–271, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1515/itit-2017-0031.
51. M. Pournader, Y. Shi, S. Seuring, and S. C. L. Koh, "Blockchain applications in supply chains, transport and logistics: a systematic review of the literature," *Int J Prod Res*, vol. 58, no. 7, pp. 2063–2081, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1080/00207543.2019.1650976.
52. Fedotova, O. Kryvoruchko, V. Shynkarenko, N. Bocharova, L. Sotnychenko, and S. Dimitrakieva, "Using the elements from a fuzzy sets theory in the process of diagnosing the loyalty of consumers of motor transport services," *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*, vol. 3, no. 3 (99), pp. 39–49, May 2019, doi: 10.15587/1729-4061.2019.169079.
53. S. Dimitrakieva, K. Atanasova, and O. Kostadinov, "Pools in Tramp Shipping and the Rules on Competition Given the Art. 101 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union," *Strategies for Policy in Science and Education-Strategii na Obrazovatelnata i Nauchnata Politika*, vol. 31, no. 3s, pp. 140–147, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.53656/str2023-3s-11-poo.
54. Conev and D. Dimitrakiev, "Use of modern technologies at Naval Academy Varna," in *Proceedings of the International Association of Maritime Universities Conference, 2023*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85185220315&partnerID=40&md5=52f8526ae19b20716c7107d83f1b524a>
55. S. Dimitrakieva, D. Milev, and C. Atanasova, "Voyage of Learning: Cruise Ships Weather Routing and Maritime Education," *Strategies for Policy in Science and Education-Strategii na Obrazovatelnata i Nauchnata Politika*, vol. 31, no. 6s, pp. 48–55, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.53656/str2023-6s-4-voy.
56. D. Dimitrakiev, V. Stankov, and C. Atanasova, "Simulator Training – Unique Powerful Instrument for Educating, Skills Creating, Mitigating Skills and Resilience Creating," *Strategies for Policy in Science and Education-Strategii na Obrazovatelnata i Nauchnata Politika*, vol. 31, no. 6s, pp. 103–111, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.53656/str2023-6s-9-sim.